

**UNLOCKING SUCCESS: THE PEER ASSISTED STUDY SESSION (P.A.S.S)
CHRONICLES- A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY OF TUTEE, TUTOR,
AND TEACHER PERSPECTIVES**

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Unlocking Success: The Peer Assisted Study Session (P.A.S.S) Chronicles- A Multiple Case Study of Tutee, Tutor, and Teacher Perspectives

Mariel A. Sarita,* Kristy Jane R. Muegna
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This qualitative multiple case study aimed to gain a deep understanding of how tutees, tutors, and teachers navigate challenges within the Peer Assisted Study Session (P.A.S.S) school program. It delved into the experiences of one tutee, one tutor, and one teacher who actively involved in the program. Through in-depth interviews, observations, and field notes, comprehensive data were gathered. Thematic analysis and cross-case analysis were utilized, revealing that participants found the program beneficial academically and socially, contributing to their personal and professional growth. Despite challenges, the tutee and tutor strived and find motivation through the support from their family and friends, fostering a positive outlook, enjoying the program, and employing strategies for academic success and personal development. Realizations about the program's academic and social impact, its role in tutors' growth, and its potential to help students on academic probation were key drivers for participation.

Keywords: *academic probation, peer tutoring, case study, motivation, challenges*

Introduction

The academic success of students in higher education is of paramount importance, and addressing the needs of students facing academic challenges is a pressing concern. Academic policies in higher education address institutional academic standards and student requirements including academic underachievement. Academic probation is virtually every institution's challenge, but it is the most under-researched policy practiced at most community colleges. It is one academic policy designed to alert students that they are not meeting the minimum academic standards of the institution. Many college students who receive low grades are placed on academic probation and may ultimately be dismissed from the institution. Thus, it becomes expedient to research on suitable intervention to where it can significantly impact their future academic performance and overall well-being (Agnes, 2019).

In the global setting, particularly in Bangladesh, a considerable proportion of students enrolled in private universities have experience academic probation especially in their first year mainly caused by poor study habits, weak writing and presentation skills, poor English language understanding, and other factors. Thus, many of them struggle to achieve success in their future academic endeavors. Students facing academic probation are more prone to encountering numerous academic difficulties and, regrettably, are at a higher risk of dropping out of university (Jony, 2022). Meanwhile, in the Philippine context specifically in Laguna State Polytechnic University,

Los Baños, a research investigation revealed that the students are having a hard time in their academics since the institution has adopted a more rigorous retention policy for students in accounting courses within their boarding program. Consequently, an incoming second-year students are required to maintain a minimum overall grade of 85%, with no grades lower than 83% in accounting courses. While this policy has led some students to improve academically, others have experienced heightened anxiety as they strive to meet these grade requirements. This anxiety has, in turn, affected their motivation, especially for those students who might end up on academic probation (Sarmiento & Macatangop, 2021 as cited in Espinosa et al., 2023).

The study holds social relevance as it addresses a crucial aspect of education and student support. It will offer a comprehensive perspective that can inform the development and improvement of peer tutoring programs, making it a valuable contribution to the field of education and, in turn, society's pursuit of equitable and quality education. The findings of this study may serve as a reference point for future research and educational initiatives. On the other hand, the study needs urgent research attention to assess the impact of Peer Assisted Study Sessions (P.A.S.S.) on student success in educational settings. It aimed to provide critical insights into the effectiveness of Project

P.A.S.S. from the perspectives of tutees, tutors, and teachers, which can inform evidence-based decision-making in education. As peer-assisted learning gains popularity, this research addressed the pressing demand for empirical data to enhance educational strategies and support student achievement. Therefore, this study was timely and necessary because its findings have the potential to shape the future of peer-assisted learning initiatives, making it a crucial endeavor for educators, administrators, and students alike.

There were various studies that were being conducted which is somewhat similar to this study such as the study being conducted by Cuizon (2022) entitled, "Peer Tutoring: An Intervention to Improve Learners' Involvement in Performance Task" and that of Wolf (2018) entitled, "The Impact of a Peer-Tutoring Model on the Academic Performance of Secondary Students". These studies have provided valuable insights into the impact of peer tutoring in students' academic performance in university contexts. However, while these existing literatures focused on the efficiency of the structure of the applied peer tutoring programs, or on the program's advantages for the tutee's, limited research has shown concern about the gains of the peer tutors themselves and the identification of areas where enhancement initiatives can be effectively implemented. This specific study sought to bridge the gap by conducting a multiple case

study to provide a more nuanced and context-specific assessment of the program's effectiveness. This includes assessing the impact on diverse student populations, exploring the reasons behind its success or limitations, and ultimately, offering insights for tailored improvements in the future. In essence, the research gap lied in the detailed exploration of Project P.A.S.S's impact and the development of informed strategies for its enhancement. Thus, these premises prompted me to propose this study.

Research Questions

This research aimed to find out the experiences of tutees, tutors and teachers in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology on the implementation of Peer Assisted Study Session (P.A.S.S). Therefore, important questions that tackled were as follows:

1. What are the unique cases of participants engaged in P.A.S.S school program?
2. What are the experiences and challenges faced by each case in the implementation of peer- assisted study session (P.A.S.S) program?
3. How does each case cope with the challenges they face during the implementation of peer- assisted study session (P.A.S.S) program?
4. What are the insights of each case that they can share to others and to the academe in general?

Literature Review

Peer Assisted Study Session

The Peer Assisted Study Session program is a voluntary initiative offering students weekly academic support through collaborative group study guided by fellow peers. PASS seeks to aid students in difficult subjects by deepening their grasp of course content, assessing their understanding of intricate topics, fostering confidence through active dialogue, and encouraging collaborative problem-solving (Wilkinson, 2019). Siddiqi et al. (2020) illustrated that peer-assisted learning effectively cultivates a relaxed and student-centered environment, leading to improved subject understanding and enhanced test performance among undergraduate medical students. Student feedback indicated that they perceived peer leaders as more accessible than laboratory instructors, facilitating a deeper comprehension of the material. (Mcintosh, 2019) add that peer Assisted Study Sessions, supported by academic tutors, serve as an essential mechanism for fostering creativity, innovation, and resilience among students, aligning with the overarching objectives of higher education.

Academic and Social Impact of Peer Tutoring

Participating in peer-assisted learning significantly enhances the academic abilities of accounting students, particularly in critical domains like critical thinking, time management, and communication skills. Aggarao et al., (2023) emphasizes the vital role of promoting students' active involvement in such initiatives to bolster both their academic prowess and social skills. According to Moeyaert et al. (2019), utilizing peer-assisted learning as an additional educational strategy produces a noteworthy and beneficial impact on the academic and social development of students. Peer tutoring demonstrated a noteworthy positive influence on both academic and social-behavioral results. Thus, educators should consider incorporating peer tutoring as a reliable approach to enhance students' academic abilities and social-behavioral outcomes.

Austin (2018) adds that peer tutoring effectively enhances the development of creativity and problem-solving skills in both tutors and tutees. The interactive nature of peer tutoring aids tutors in comprehending the cognitive abilities of the tutees and their grasp of the subject matter. It offers students the advantage of engaging in discussions that foster learning within a friendly atmosphere.

Personal and Professional Impact of Peer Tutoring

Monaghan (2023) revealed that students who participated in positions such as peer tutors or classroom assistants within peer tutoring or cross-age tutoring initiatives saw notable benefits. These roles improved tutors' understanding of the subjects they taught, increased their confidence and self- belief, and encouraged qualities such as accountability and compassion. They gain insights into the learning journey and develop a deeper appreciation for the teaching profession. Orsini et al. (2021) claimed and affirmed that peer tutoring has a profound impact on both the professional development and personal growth of individuals involved, shaping them into more capable educators and empathetic individuals. This valuable experience equips them with a varied range of skills that they can apply to their future careers in education.

Seeking Assistance from More Knowledgeable Others

Seeking assistance in academics has been shown to enhance students' capacity to overcome obstacles, ultimately contributing to their academic achievements. Li et al. (2023) emphasized that in an increasingly competitive academic environment, the significance of students actively seeking and utilizing academic support is widely acknowledged as crucial for enriching their educational journey and boosting their performance. This underscores the vital role of seeking guidance from individuals with greater expertise. Almaghaslah et al. (2022) found that university students encounter difficulty when confronting academic hurdles independently, often resorting to seeking assistance. The research revealed that the primary motivations behind seeking help were positive factors, such as enhancing

learning further and striving to successfully complete courses.

Motivation and Employment of Diverse Teaching Strategies

It is significant to employ a variety of teaching methods to enhance student motivation and learning. Tremblay-Wragg et al. (2020) emphasized that utilizing between six and nine different teaching strategies, instructors observed an increase in student motivation for certain groups throughout the semester, while others experienced static or diminished motivation levels. This emphasizes the necessity of considering diverse teaching strategy to foster positive learning outcomes. Chetry et al. (2023) found that utilizing inventive teaching methods grounded in the framework of Multiple Intelligences Theory (MIT) has the potential to enhance academic achievements and advance fair educational opportunities, concurrently nurturing essential 21st-century competencies in both students and educators.

Difficulty in Tutoring due to Lack of Preparations

Ling (2018) found that peer tutors encountered difficulties related to the commitment of tutees, communication, time management, and inadequate knowledge. These obstacles led to a decline in some tutors' passion for teaching and their desire to fulfill their roles as peer tutors. It is also important for a tutor to be well prepared to play their roles and responsibilities. Jawhari (2021) add that a key drawback of peer-assisted learning, noted by tutors, is their lack of experience. This common concern in peer teaching research highlights that while peer tutors may have less expertise than senior faculty, they compensate through diligent efforts and comprehensive preparations to succeed in their tutoring responsibilities. Murtisari et al. (2020) added that difficulties encountered by tutors, encompass motivating students, preparing and organizing materials, and addressing varying levels of proficiency. The Impact of Academic Probation

Academic probation denotes the academic status assigned to students who fail to meet the university's predetermined minimum grade point average requirements. Agnes (2018) found that academic probation can lead to decreased motivation and added a feeling of disappointment among students who feel disconnected from their peer groups. On the other hand, Sani et al. (2021) stress that implementing probation had a beneficial impact on students, inspiring them to exert additional effort to address their shortcomings, improve their academic performance, and fulfill graduation criteria successfully. Espinosa et al. (2023) found that students viewed the enforcement of academic probation positively, as it encouraged diligence, resilience, and improved time management. This, in turn, enhanced their communication with parents and positively impacted their educational journey. Implementing Effective Time Management

Effective time management not only contributes to academic success and reduced stress levels but also empowers students to better balance their personal and academic lives, fostering a more well- rounded college experience (Alshutwi et al., 2019). Time management is key to creating an organized, engaging learning environment. By prioritizing tasks and using effective tools, educators, students, and parents can enhance the teaching and learning process (Ghafar, 2024). Efficient time management prevents overwhelm and underproductivity. Task prioritization is key to optimizing productivity, reducing stress, and ensuring a balanced use of time (Chaudhari, 2022).

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research design, specifically utilizing a multiple case study approach. As noted by Rashid et. al. (2019), qualitative case studies offer a detailed examination of a specific event in a particular context. Additionally, this study design incorporated a systematic process for gathering data through interviews and interactive discussions, which helps in understanding experiences, viewpoints, insights, and specific observable situations.

Participants

The primary participants in this study were carefully chosen to provide rich and valuable data in understanding the research problem and central phenomenon. The researcher purposely selected two (2) tutees, two (2) peer tutors and two (2) teachers who provided perspectives on the implementation of Peer Assisted Study Sessions (P.A.S.S) school program. Overall, there were three (3) main participants and three (3) informants in this study. Each of the participants underwent in- depth interviews, the researcher conducted individual interviews with them to gather their experiences and challenges during the P.A.S.S program.

Procedure

To collect data for this study, the researcher followed a structured protocol throughout the study, encompassing every phase from pre-interview preparations to post-interview procedures. The researcher developed interview guide questions, which were then validated by a panel of experts. Afterward, the researcher obtained an endorsement letter and sought approval from the advisor to proceed with the study. Approval was then requested from the institution's administration to conduct face-to-face interviews with selected instructors and students.

After receiving the necessary approvals, the researcher sent consent letters to selected participants. If they agreed, a consent form was provided for signature. Following approval from the validation panel, the study began with an orientation session for participants, explaining the study's purpose, methodology, and participants' rights, including permission to record the interviews. Afterward, the

researcher ensured the confidentiality of the recordings, transcribed the data, and had participants verify the transcripts. The verified data was then translated, analyzed, and used to draw conclusions and recommendations.

Data Analysis

The collected data from the in-depth interviews were transcribed, translated, and analyzed following Creswell's (2009) proposed process for data analysis. The researcher followed the steps recommended by Creswell. The responses of the participants, once translated, were systematically coded to facilitate a thematic analysis of the data within this case study. Thematic analysis, often referred to as coding, encompasses the process of categorizing responses and identifying recurring themes in the text to construct a structured representation of thematic concepts. These discernible themes offered valuable insights within the data, which can be furthered subjected to analysis and measurement.

Through the systematic process of thematic analysis, the researcher organized the dataset into themes or patterns. This enabled the researcher to identify and develop themes based on the obtained data, as described by Dye (2021). Throughout the data analysis phase, the researcher heavily depended on the transcripts and translated versions of the informants' responses. Employing a systematic coding process, the researcher categorized and structured the recurring responses to formulate an exhaustive thematic analysis. These concepts were methodically arranged and assessed, considering their interrelationships, commonalities, and distinctions, with the support of a data analyst.

Ethical Considerations

When gathering data from individuals, researchers must follow ethical principles to ensure integrity, validity, and the protection of participants' rights. Ethical guidelines help maintain academic standards, improve research quality, and safeguard the well-being of participants (Bhandari, 2022). Formalizing consent protects individuals' right to choose participation and fosters trust in research (Klykken, 2021). Ensuring voluntary, informed decisions is essential for valid consent.

In this study, I uphold the concept of autonomy which involves providing participants with clear and understandable information about the nature and purpose of the research, as outlined in the participant information leaflet. I maintained confidentiality by assigning each participant a discreet code to protect their anonymity, in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. No identifying information, such as name or occupation, was collected, and participants were not asked for their names on any forms. The researcher personally transcribed the interviews to further safeguard privacy.

Benevolence was upheld by the researcher selecting a secure location for interviews, prioritizing participant safety, and providing a safe space for open, judgment-free discussion. To minimize psychological risks, interview data was kept confidential, reducing the potential for negative consequences such as shame or embarrassment. In the pursuit of justice, participants incurred no expenses, and their contributions were fully recognized. The researcher valued each participant's input and expressed gratitude through practical gestures to acknowledge their participation. These ethical principles—respect for autonomy, confidentiality, beneficence, and justice—were consistently upheld to ensure the protection and fair treatment of all participants.

Results and Discussion

A qualitative approach was employed to explore the participants' unique characteristics, experiences, challenges, and insights. Guided by this approach, the researcher conducted a multiple- case study to gather data from the target respondents. The study aims to demonstrate that the multiple-case study design is an effective method for gaining in-depth understanding of a situation and providing a rich context for investigating the phenomena (Tomaszewski et al., 2020). Three cases were examined, each involving a participant and an informant. The researcher conducted interviews with both the participants and informants, and the findings were analyzed individually for each case.

Table 1. *Experiences and Challenges Faced by Each Case in the Implementation of P.A.S.S Program*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Building a Positive Tutor-Tutee Relationship	<p>“It feels good because I have met someone new, and at the same time, that person has greatly helped me in my academics.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“She was given time to bond with her tutor, and a new friendship was also formed.” - IDI-02</p> <p>“So, the most memorable part is when you become close to your tutee, another friend, not just in terms of discussing academic difficulties but also in casual conversations, getting to know them not only as a student but also as a person outside of school.” - IDI-03</p> <p>“It is when they developed a bond where they became close of her tutee, from initially being strangers. They became close, and she also help her.” - IDI-04</p>
Struggling on Time and Availability	<p>“We just could not avoid facing challenges, like conflicts in our schedules. That time appears to be her only free time, and I have classes during that period, so we cannot meet.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“The problems we have faced during the implementation of project P.A.S.S. include occasional conflicts in our tutor's schedule. There are times when our tutor is unavailable to teach us, and we have to wait until the following week. This complicates things for us as our schedules clash.” - IDI-02</p> <p>“Me and my tutee need to meet halfway because our schedules do not match. If she is not available at this time, I</p>

	will adjust. If I am available at this time and she is not, both of us will make adjustments.” - IDI-03
	“Time management remains a challenge because, of course, they are both students. As a tutor, she has her classes, and her tutee also has classes, so there is a conflict in their availability for tutoring or study sessions.” - IDI-04
	“Some challenges encountered during the implementation of the P.A.S.S program include scheduling conflicts then varying levels of engagement of the tutees.” - IDI-06
Difficulty in Tutoring Due to Lack of Preparation	“If you are a tutor, you should be prepared on what you are going to teach; if you are not ready yourself, of course you will not be able to teach. Sometimes, she does not know how to answer if I have a specific difficulty in that subject.” - IDI-01
	“The tutor sometimes struggles in disseminating information to us about this topic. There are also instances when it is difficult for them to explain the lessons to us effectively.” - IDI- 02
	“The other students who are on probation and serve as tutees are not very active in participating during class discussions. Some are busy, while others are already delighted because they will be shifting to another program. Therefore, the lack of active participation from our tutees seems to be the main problem with the implementation.” - IDI-05
	“Challenges encountered during the implementation of the P.A.S.S program include scheduling conflicts then varying levels of engagement of the tutees.” - IDI-06

Experiences of Tutee, Tutor, and Teacher

After analyzing the data, it was concluded that the participants had shared similar experiences with the P.A.S.S program. It was found that the experiences of the participants were building a positive tutor-tutee relationship, struggling on time and availability, and difficulty in tutoring due to lack of preparations. These themes aligned with existing literature and theories, elucidating the complex experiences of tutees, tutors, and teachers who participated on the implementation of the Project P.A.S.S.

Building A Positive Tutor-Tutee Relationship

The study revealed that tutees and tutors developed a strong bond with each other, fostering a sense of camaraderie and friendship during the intervention program. Peer tutors benefited academically through exchanging knowledge with their peers while also having the opportunity to cultivate lasting friendships and foster positive relationships with a wide range of other students (Al Kharusi, 2018). A positive, trusting bond between tutor and tutee establishes a platform for openly discussing any necessary adjustments in study routines (Marx & Wolf, 2018).

Struggling on Time and Availability

Time constraints and availability often pose significant challenges, as both tutors and tutees juggle various commitments. Struggling to synchronize schedules can hinder the effectiveness of tutoring sessions, disrupting learning progress. This is in accordance from Garcia et al. (2018) and Chai and Lin (2019), who noted that time constraints, along with potential cultural appropriation issues in peer coaching, may pose obstacles requiring attention. The demand for availability and the intricacies of scheduling posed significant challenges, underscoring the necessity for careful consideration and strategic planning.

Difficulty in Tutoring due to Lack of Preparations

Lack of preparations significantly hinder the effectiveness of tutoring sessions. Without adequate preparation, tutors may struggle to understand the material themselves, leading to confusion and ineffective instruction for their peers. It conforms on the claim of Ling (2018) which stated that it is important for a tutor to be well prepared to play their roles and responsibilities. Insufficient readiness for their roles poses a significant challenge for both the tutors and tutees. They need comprehensive preparations to succeed in their tutoring responsibilities (Jawhari, 2021).

Table 2. Coping Mechanisms of Each Case with the Challenges Faced on the Implementation of P.A.S.S. Program

Emerging Themes	Supporting Statements
Implementing Effective Time Management	“Regarding on our conflict in time, what we did was, we set a schedule and a specific time and at least 1 to 2 hours to attend and to at least have her tutor me. We just set a schedule, and after his class or my class during that time, we would really meet.” - IDI-01 “We really set a schedule for our study sessions to avoid conflicts with our other commitments, as we also have jobs. Setting a specific time is our way of ensuring that our tutor can teach us effectively.” - IDI-02 “To effectively manage my time, I arrange and list my daily tasks. I create a to-do list, including scheduled study sessions with my tutee. I strive every day to stay focused and avoid laziness.” - IDI-03 “They set a schedule for their tutoring sessions and also, she maintains to-do lists, outlining her daily tasks. If they cannot meet face to face, they conduct sessions online. These are the things that I have observed in their routine.” - IDI-04
Seeking Assistance from More Knowledgeable Others	“I seek help from my co-tutors, as I mentioned earlier, and from our program coordinator. I rely on them, especially when I encounter difficulties in understanding the lesson or assisting my tutee.” - IDI-03 “Just as I mentioned earlier, I believe in seeking advice from her co-tutors, and of course, consulting the program head when she has questions about what steps to take for her to be more effective as a tutor and to truly assist her

	tutee academically.” - IDI-04
	“I am asking help with our assistant dean particularly with regards to someone who has stopped because they no longer want to pursue education, especially those tutees who are not participating because they claim to be tired and are no longer interested in education. So, I am asking for help with my immediate supervisor.” - IDI-05
	“Seek help from a fellow educator like us within the program, so collaborating with other teachers to brainstorm solutions and sharing best practices has been instrumental in overcoming challenges.” - IDI-06
Having a Positive Outlook and Goal-Oriented Mindset	“I just enjoy every moment, especially in our encounters with my tutor. Also, I always think that this program can truly help me to get out of my probationary status, so I can return to normal and become a regular student again.” - IDI-01
	“We really instill in our mindset that thanks for the project P.A.S.S. because we are given the opportunity to learn and, at the same time, to further motivate us, during this project P.A.S.S., we truly embed in our mind that this is our gateway to return as regular students.” - IDI-02
	“I direct my attention towards the goal of this P.A.S.S program, not really minding the exhaustion. What I focus on is that at the end of the day, my efforts are worth it because I know that my tutee will improve academically.” - IDI-03
	“I think she really hones in on her goal, paying no mind to exhaustion, and remains dedicated to the program's goal. The fulfilling part for her is that, at the end of the day, it seems like the experiences on her part are quite fulfilling.” - IDI-04

Coping Mechanisms of Tutee, Tutor, and Teacher

After collecting and analyzing the data from the participants, it was found that they employed a variety of coping mechanisms to deal with the challenges encountered during the implementation of the P.A.S.S program. The researcher identified three themes: implementing effective time management, seeking assistance from more knowledgeable others and having a positive outlook and goal-oriented mindset.

Implementing Effective Time Management

The study revealed that effective time management can be achieved by establishing a structured agenda for each session, allowing both the tutor and the tutee stay focused and make the most of their time together. Alshutwi et al. (2019), found that the proficiency in time management among college students stands out as a crucial attribute for maintaining strong academic performance. This insight also aligns with Ghafar (2024), who found that time management presents an opportunity for acquiring fresh skills and knowledge. By prioritizing tasks and using time management tools, educators and learners can create an organized, engaging learning environment with fewer interruptions.

Seeking Assistance from More Knowledgeable Others

It was found that seeking assistance from more knowledgeable others fosters a supportive learning environment where students can clarify concepts and deepen their understanding through peer interaction. It mirrors the idea of Li et al. (2023) and Almaghaslah et al. (2022), who claimed that seeking assistance in academics has been shown to enhance students' capacity to overcome obstacles, ultimately contributing to their academic achievements. When confronting academic hurdles independently, they often resorting to seeking assistance. In an increasingly competitive academic environment, the significance of students actively seeking and utilizing academic support is widely acknowledged as crucial for enriching their educational journey and boosting their performance.

Having a Positive Outlook and Goal-Oriented Mindset

Maintaining a positive outlook fosters an environment of encouragement and support, motivating both the tutor and the tutee. Fostering behaviors conducive to enhancing the academic lives of students hinges on maintaining optimal levels of motivation and cultivating a mindset centered on task-oriented goals within educational environments (Supervía et al. 2019). A positive mindset nurtured throughout one's academic journey serves as a cornerstone for future accomplishments in higher education and professional endeavors (Sienna & Slate, 2024).

Table 3. *Insights of Each Case in the Implementation of P.A.S.S. Program*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Academic and Social Impact of Peer Tutoring	“This really helped me with my academics. Her help extended beyond our tutoring sessions, as she not only taught me the subject matter but also became a person with whom I could share my personal problems. Through this, we built a bond and formed a friendship during the P.A.S.S program.” - IDI- 01
	“Her comprehension has significantly improved, and her academic performance has become even better. Thanks to Project P.A.S.S, and also because of the tutor, our understanding in academics has greatly improved. We truly feel that we have learned a lot during our discussions and it gives us an opportunity to meet a new person that became our tutor and friend.” - IDI-02
	“Aside from the tutee receiving academic assistance, they were also given a kind of like a mentor figure whom they could share with and provide support amidst their situations.” - IDI- 03
	“This program, I think, can be very helpful, providing significant assistance to students academically, especially

those who are under probation. Of course, there are tutors who will extend help to them to prevent them from falling behind in the education program.” - IDI-04

“This really form a big impact with their academics because they have fellow students, and it seems like there's no barrier since they aren't afraid to ask questions. All they need to do is actively engage in the implementation, take it seriously, and they will truly learn in their enrolled subjects. Additionally, they can gain extra insights from tutors, who happen to be our President's Listers, and have formed close friendships during study sessions.” - IDI-05

“Sir can share with others who participated in the P.A.S.S program the importance of student-centered learning and the effectiveness of peer-assisted study session in improving academic performance of the students, so emphasizing the value of collaboration and creating a supportive learning community could benefit students academically and socially.” - IDI-06

Provided a Personal and Professional Growth to Both Parties

“This is really a great help to lift us from our probationary status. It truly assists us, especially in our academics. When faced with challenges, we have someone to turn to, and we would not hesitate to ask questions or seek guidance from our instructors. It is reassuring to know that we are given a chance and an opportunity for support, eliminating the need for us to approach them, as they are the ones providing the assistance to help us overcome this probationary period.” - IDI-01

“Just always be participative because it will also contribute to the success of this program, and helps other probationary students like us who can be assisted to regain their status as regular students again.” - IDI-02

So, it has a significant impact not only on the tutee who benefited but also on me as a tutor because here, I practice my teaching, making my patience grow, especially since I am a future educator.” - IDI-03

“Also, through this project P.A.S.S., we actively utilize and apply our teaching skills on our tutee during our study sessions and while instructing our tutees.” - IDI-04

The Importance of Motivation and Employment of Diverse Teaching Strategies

“Not because he is under probationary status as a student means he is academically weak. There are other factors that influenced him to end up in that situation. So, let us not judge hastily because we are not aware of the story behind why he is in that situation. Instead of passing judgment, we should support them, boost their confidence, and encourage active participation in their classes. Let us strive for their academic improvement.” - IDI-03

“We should not easily judge students under probation because I know that some students feel degraded due to that status. They are often labeled as not good academically. However, we should always remember that there are many factors involved in why they find themselves in that situation.” - IDI- 04

“The teachers should practice differentiated instructions as well as a varied and diversified teaching strategies in the class so that they will be able to cater the varied learning needs, interests and wants of our students and so with that maybe somehow all of our students will be participating because we are trying to impose and dissect varied learning needs and strategies inside the classroom.” - IDI-05

“I guess the suggestion for enhancing the P.A.S.S program include providing more training and resources for tutor, creating more structured curriculum and exploring ways to integrate technology for more interactive sessions. So, encouraging open communication and feedback loops among participants could also enhance the program's effectiveness.” - IDI-06

Insights of Tutee, Tutor, and Teacher

At this point, after analyzing the data, the researcher identifies key themes that captured the insights of tutees, tutors, and teachers during the implementation of the P.A.S.S program. The researcher identified three important themes: academic and social impact of peer tutoring, provided a personal and professional growth to both parties and the importance of motivation and employment of diverse teaching strategies.

Academic and Social Impact of Peer Tutoring

The peer-assisted study session program has been found to enhance academic performance by offering personalized support and reinforcing learning through peer interaction, while also fostering social development, empathy, communication skills, and a sense of community. In line with this, Aggarao et al. (2023) found that Peer-assisted learning significantly improves students' academic skills, especially in critical thinking, time management, and communication. This insight also aligns with Moeyaert et al. (2019), who found that peer tutoring has a noteworthy positive influence on both academic and social-behavioral aspect of the students.

Provided a Personal and Professional Growth to Both Parties

The study revealed that peer tutoring fosters growth for both tutors and tutees, with tutors enhancing their teaching skills and understanding, while tutees gain confidence and mastery through personalized support. It mirrors the idea of (Orsini et al. 2021) who found that peer tutoring has a profound impact on both the professional development and personal growth of individuals involved, shaping them into more capable educators and empathetic individuals. Students in peer tutor roles gained significant benefits, including a deeper understanding of the subjects, increased confidence, and the development of accountability and compassion (Monaghan, 2023).

The Importance of Motivation and Employment of Diverse Teaching Strategies

The study revealed that motivation drives learning, boosting students' engagement and persistence. Using diverse teaching strategies ensures inclusivity and addresses various learning styles, creating a dynamic educational environment. Tremblay-Wragg et al. (2019)

found that using a range of teaching methods in university courses enhance student motivation and learning. Utilizing between six and nine different teaching strategies, instructors observed an increase in student motivation for certain groups throughout the semester, suggesting that employing diverse teaching methods can better engage students.

Conclusions

The participants have shared their authentic experiences regarding their involvement in the Peer Assisted Study Session (P.A.S.S) school program. These findings indicated the need for specific improvements within the program to enhance the learning environment, particularly for tutors and especially tutees who are under academic probation. Consequently, this research contributed to the advancement to the body of knowledge in fostering inclusivity and collaboration.

Future research should prioritize evaluating the impact of intervention programs on the experiences of all stakeholders, with a particular emphasis on incorporating student perspectives into evaluative research. Ultimately, leveraging insights from future studies can enhance inclusion and support systems for all involved parties, fostering a more conducive institutional environment.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Mariel A. Sarita

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Kristy Jane R. Muegna, PhD

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines